

Determination of total organic carbon in lower Mahadek sandstones of Meghalaya (India) and its correlation with uranium

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Abstract : Uranium deposits hosted lower Mahadek sandstones of Meghalaya (India) are one of the largest and richest [average grade of $\sim 0.1\%$ ${}^e\text{U}_3\text{O}_8$] of its kind in India. The paper deals with quantification of total organic carbon [TOC] in these sandstones by Walkley-Black procedure. The readily oxidisable organic carbon is oxidised with chromic acid in the presence of excess sulphuric acid without external heat applied. The excess dichromate ion is determined by titration with standard ammonium iron(II) sulphate and the amount of oxidised material is calculated from the quantity of dichromate reduced. The TOC values along with loss on ignition [LOI] and moisture [H_2O^-] contents were correlated with uranium in these mineralised rocks.

Keywords : Quantification of TOC, uranium, LOI, H_2O^- , lower Mahadek mineralised sandstones.

Introduction

Uranium in the sandstone hosted uranium deposit at Domiasiat and Wakhyn, Meghalaya is mainly associated with organic matter, which is also enriched in several trace elements, viz. Zn, Cu, Ni, V, Co, Ba, Sn, Mo, Cr, Ag, P etc. Most of the uranium in the ore occurs closely associated with organic matter, occurring in various forms such as lumps, veins, layers, fracture fillings, coatings and disseminations in the host arenite. Some of the organic matter lumps are abnormally rich in uranium, analysing as high as 40% U_3O_8 ¹. Many elements, including uranium, vanadium, copper, molybdenum, iron, selenium, arsenic, phosphorous, sulfur, oxygen, manganese, chromium, nitrogen, carbon and others, occur in more than one oxidation state in nature and participate in natural redox reactions². Of these elements, only a few are sufficiently abundant in sedimentary environments to be able to transfer enough electrons in redox reactions to have a major influence on the overall redox state of the solution. Present paper describes quantification of TOC and LOI and moisture, followed by data interpretation for their correlation with uranium.

The strong association of organic matter with uranium deposits in sedimentary rocks and the change in the character of the deposits from physical to chemical con-

centrations concomitant with the change in the oxidation state of the atmosphere indicate that reduction is the most important chemical process involving organic matter in the genesis of uranium deposits. Although organic matter is a stronger reductant than hydrogen sulfide, experiments have shown that hydrogen sulfide is a more aggressive reductant (less kinetically inhibited) and in some deposits, hydrogen sulfide, derived from the reduction of sulfate by organic matter may have reduced uranium. Once uranium deposits were formed, organic matter maintained a reducing environment, which protected the deposits from oxidation and destruction. Consequently, organic matter or reduced sulfur is the reductants available to precipitate uranium minerals in various types of sedimentary deposits.

The exact determination and characterization of organic carbon in solid samples is one of the most extensively performed analyses in geological studies³. Organic matter in soils and sediments is widely distributed over the earth's surface occurring in almost all terrestrial and aquatic environments. Important characteristics of the organic matter include their ability to form water-soluble and water insoluble complexes with metal ions and hydrous oxides; interact with clay minerals and bind particles together; sorb and desorb both naturally occurring

and anthropogenically-introduced organic compounds; absorb and release plant nutrients; and hold water in soil environment. As a result of these characteristics, the determination of total organic carbon is an essential part of any site characterization since its presence or absence can markedly influence how chemicals will react in the soil or sediment.

Experimental

Reagents : All reagents used were prepared from analytical grade chemicals. All stock solutions were stored in polyethylene laboratory ware, thoroughly washed in hot 10% (v/v) hydrochloric acid, and repeatedly rinsed with distilled water before use.

Standard solutions :

(a) The potassium dichromate solution (0.1667 *M*) was prepared by dissolving 49.04 g of potassium dichromate (GR, Merck) in 1000 mL pure distilled water and stored into a 1000 mL volumetric flask.

(b) The ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (0.5 *N*) was prepared by dissolving ferrous ammonium sulphate (GR, Merck) in distilled water containing 10 mL of 1 : 1 H₂SO₄ and made upto 250 mL.

Procedure :

Determination of Total Organic Carbon : The standard wet chemistry technique for the sample extraction involves the rapid dichromate oxidation of organic matter. Perhaps the best known of the rapid dichromate oxidation is the Walkley-Black procedure⁴. In this procedure, accurately weigh 0.1 to 1 g (depending upon the organic carbon content) of the sample, followed by addition of 10 mL standard dichromate solution (0.1667 *M*) and 20 mL concentrated sulphuric acid and gently swirl for about 30 s. The solution is allowed to cool prior to adding water to halt the reaction. The end-point of the titration is more easily determined with a cold mixture. Add 3 to 4 drops of ferroin indicator solution and titrate the excess dichromate with 0.5 *N* ammonium iron(II) sulphate solution. The colour change at the end point will be sharp, changing from blue-green to a reddish blue. Make a blank determination in the same manner to standardise the ammonium iron(II) sulphate solution.

The chemistry of extraction is as follows :

(a) Dichromate ion reacts with carbon as follows :

(b) Ferrous ion reacts with dichromate as follows :

Calculation :

Percent Oxidisable Organic Carbon (OC) :

$$\text{OC} = \frac{[(B-A) \times 0.3 \times M_A]}{W}$$

where, B = Blank titre (mL), A = Sample titre (mL), M_A = Concentration of ammonium iron(II) sulphate solution (*M*) and W = weight of dried sample (g).

Correction for total organic carbon :

The method described above gives typical recoveries varying from less than 65% to more than 85%. Therefore, the use of 1.3 as a correction factor is recommended,

Total Organic Carbon (percent) = Oxidisable organic carbon × 1.3

Interferences : Fe²⁺ and Cl⁻ lead to positive errors in TOC determination, and MnO₂ leads to negative error of TOC content. Fe²⁺ may be removed from the sample by oxidation (i.e. air-drying). Excess Cl⁻ in a sample interferes through the formation of chromyl chloride (CrO₂Cl₂). Excessive Cl⁻ may be removed by leaching the sample or through precipitation, as AgCl, by adding Ag₂SO₄ to the H₂SO₄ used during digestion process. If large quantities of MnO₂ are present, pretreatment of the sample with FeSO₄ will remove this interference. The samples of lower Mahadeks does not contain significant amount of chloride and manganese, hence does not affected the determination.

Determination of uranium : Uranium was determined by laser induced fluorimetry as described⁵.

Determination of loss on ignition : It involves removal of all volatiles (organic and inorganic carbon, moisture, water of crystallisation, etc.). A known weight of the sample is placed in porcelain crucible, which is then heated at 1000 °C for 1 h. The sample is then cooled in the desiccator and weighed. Semi-empirically, LOI is calculated

as the difference between the initial and final sample weights by the initial sample weight times 100%. The moisture content [H₂O⁻] is known by weight loss at 110 °C for 1 h. In lower Mahadeks, the LOI may be attributed to the volatiles, like organic carbon, SO₂, water held in crystal and moisture. TOC mentioned in the text under cold condition (i.e. without external heat applied) is only readily oxidisable organic carbon.

Determination of major, minor and trace elements : The major, minor and trace constituents of rocks were determined by ICP-OES, AAS, UV-Vis spectrophotometry, flame photometry, titrimetry etc.

Results and discussion

The analytical results for uranium, TOC, LOI and moisture contents in mineralised rocks of lower Mahadek sandstones, Meghalaya (India) are shown in Table 1. The results show that uranium is positively correlated with

Sl. No.	Sample code	% U ₃ O ₈	% TOC	% LOI	% H ₂ O ⁻
1.	B-11	0.81	0.71	3.29	0.59
2.	B-12	0.005	0.24	4.57	0.48
3.	B-13	0.018	0.16	2.77	0.47
4.	B-14	0.097	0.59	3.86	0.43
5.	B-15	4.98	5.66	48.2	4.16
6.	B-20	0.002	0.08	2.58	0.42
7.	B-21	0.003	0.08	3.59	0.54
8.	B-22	0.005	0.16	4.03	0.61
9.	B-23	0.039	0.24	2.71	0.20
10.	B-77	10.80	5.66	34.6	3.49
11.	B-78	0.074	0.71	2.11	0.41
12.	B-79	20.69	5.66	47.3	7.29

with TOC, LOI and moisture contents (Figs. 1, 2, 3). Higher concentration of uranium is linked with higher LOI in the sandstones of lower Mahadeks. The leaching

Fig. 1. Co-relation of %U₃O₈ and %TOC.

Fig. 2. Co-relation of %U₃O₈ with %LOI.

Fig. 3. Co-relation of %U₃O₈ with %H₂O⁻.

Table 2. Leaching studies carried out on uranium in mineralized rocks of lower Mahadek sandstones, Meghalaya (India)

Leaching conditions	B-11	B-14	B-15	B-23	B-77	B-78	B-79
% U ₃ O ₈ [Cold leaching, 10% HNO ₃ , 1 h]	0.74	0.041	3.33	0.009	8.94	0.025	18.59
% U ₃ O ₈ [Hot leaching, 10% HNO ₃ , 1 h]	0.77	0.073	3.89	0.015	9.50	0.052	19.52
% U ₃ O ₈ [Ignition at 600 °C, 1 h and Hot leaching, 10% HNO ₃ , 1 h]	0.80	0.074	4.96	0.016	10.76	0.058	19.66
% U ₃ O ₈ (Total, HF-HNO ₃)	0.81	0.097	4.98	0.039	10.80	0.074	20.69
Composition of mineralized rocks	B-11, 15, 77, 79 (Black coloured samples) : (%) SiO ₂ , 7.8–36.4; TiO ₂ , 0.38–1.24; Al ₂ O ₃ , 1.1–3.5; FeO, 0.22–3.1; Fe ₂ O ₃ , 4.1–24.8; CaO, 0.32–0.71; MgO, 0.1–0.5; Na ₂ O, 0.05–0.2; K ₂ O, 0.09–0.82; P ₂ O ₅ , 0.37–1.7; MnO, 0.05–0.1; LOI, 34.59–48.23; TOC, 0.71–5.66; H ₂ O ⁻ (moisture), 3.49–7.29; (ppm) Cu, 31–51; Zn, 20–8733; Mo, 28–394; Ni, 200–1697 B-14, 23, 78 (Grey coloured samples) : (%) SiO ₂ , 81.6–88.3; TiO ₂ , 0.46–0.79; Al ₂ O ₃ , 2.9–3.5; FeO, 0.14–3.6; Fe ₂ O ₃ , 0.1–8.3; CaO, 0.01–0.02; MgO, 0.01–0.3; Na ₂ O, 0.06–0.16; K ₂ O, 0.14–1.58; P ₂ O ₅ , 0.36–0.38; MnO, <0.01–0.04; LOI, 2.11–3.86; TOC, 0.24–0.71; H ₂ O ⁻ (Moisture), 0.2–0.43; (ppm) Cu, <5–8; Zn, 6–35; Mo, <10–189; Ni, <10.						

studies were also carried out on two set of samples (Table 2) and it was found that leaching was complete in the samples rich in LOI. The samples in which uranium was locked in silica quantitative recovery was not obtained (Fig. 4).

Conclusion

The lower Mahadek sandstones have fairly good uranium mineralization. High LOI and TOC containing samples were found rich in uranium. Uranium in such

type of rocks was locked in organic carbon and not in silicate matrix, which on roasting and subsequent hot leaching gave quantitative recovery. On the basis of the studies carried out on leachability of uranium vis-à-vis LOI, TOC, moisture and SiO₂ contents, it is concluded that quantitative uranium recovery is facilitated by hot leaching of roasted organic matter hosted mineralised sandstone rocks. While in case of silica rich mineralised rocks leachability of uranium is not quantitative. It is also ob-

Fig. 4. Leachability studies on uranium.

served that uranium have positive correlation with TOC values along with loss on ignition [LOI] and moisture [H₂O⁻] contents in these mineralised rocks.

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